

Equilibrium studies of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} ternary complexes with anthranilic acid derivatives and *N,N*-donor ligands

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Abstract : Equilibrium studies of (1 : 1 : 1) ternary, MAL complexes where, M = Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}, L = *N*-methyl anthranilic acid (NMAA), *N*-butyl anthranilic acid (NBAA) and *N*-phenyl anthranilic acid (NPAA) and A = 2,2-bipyridyl (bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) were carried out pH-metrically at 30 °C and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength in aqueous-ethanol (50% v/v) medium. The formation constants of the binary (ML) and ternary complexes were determined under identical conditions for better correlation. The relative stabilities of the ternary complexes are quantified in terms of the parameter, Δ log *K*. The stabilities of the complexes with respect to the ligand, L follow the order, NBAA > NMAA > NPAA. Various factors influencing the formation and stability of the complexes are discussed.

Keywords : Ligand, ternary complexes, formation constants, stability, Δ log *K*.

Introduction

The anthranilic acid derivatives, *N*-methyl anthranilic acid (NMAA), *N*-butyl anthranilic acid (NBAA) and *N*-phenyl anthranilic acid (NPAA) are known for various biological activities¹ and applications². The synthesis, characterization and biological activities of transition metal complexes of these ligands were reported³. The formation constants of some binary complexes of these ligands in solution were also reported⁴. In the present paper, we report the pH-metric equilibrium study of the ternary complexes, MAL where, M = Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}; L = NMAA, NBAA and NPAA and A = *N,N*-donor ligands: 2,2-bipyridyl (bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) in aqueous-ethanol (50% v/v) medium at 30 °C and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. For better correlation, the formation constants of the binary complexes, ML, are also determined under identical conditions.

Results and discussion

Formation of the ternary complexes was confirmed from the pH-metric titration curves and experimental data. The ternary complexes, MAL were found to form in stepwise (two step) equilibria, where in the ternary complex curve closely follow the binary (MA) complex

curve in the lower pH region until the protons of primary ligand (A) are neutralized, indicating the formation of the binary complex. Later, the divergence of the ternary curve from the binary curve at higher pH region indicate the formation⁵ of the ternary complex, MAL in the second step. Thus in the ternary complex, MAL the ligand A acts as a primary ligand and the ligand L acts as secondary ligand.

This was also confirmed from other observations such as change in intensity of colour of the complexation medium and shift in pH of precipitation compared to the corresponding binary complexes, MA and ML.

The formation constants of the ternary complexes have been evaluated and presented in Table 1. The formation constants of the binary complexes, ML were also determined under identical conditions and listed in the table. The relative stabilities of the ternary complexes were characterized in terms of the statistical parameter⁵, Δ log *K* and listed in the same table. Where,

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M$$

The stability of the ternary complexes are also expressed in terms of stability per unit base strength (SUBS)⁶ of the ligand, L where,

Table 1. Acid dissociation constants (pK_a) and formation constants of binary and ternary complexes at 30 °C and 0.1 M (KNO_3) ionic strength in aqueous-ethanol (50% v/v) medium

System	pK_a	M=Cu ^{II}		Cu ^{II} -A-L			Ni ^{II} -A-L		
		$\log K_{ML}^M$	$\Delta \log K_{ML}^M$	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS
NMAA	5.62	3.94	3.14						
NBAA	5.75	4.25	3.22						
NPAA	5.10	3.03	3.03						
phen-NMAA				2.88	-1.06	0.51	2.17	-0.97	0.39
phen-NBAA				3.03	-1.22	0.53	2.26	-0.96	0.39
phen-NPAA				2.17	-0.86	0.43	2.06	-0.97	0.40
bipy-NMAA				3.42	-0.52	0.61	3.10	-0.04	0.55
bipy-NBAA				3.68	-0.57	0.64	3.14	-0.08	0.55
bipy-NPAA				2.99	-0.04	0.58	2.87	-0.16	0.57

(Values are accurate to ± 0.05)

$$SUBS = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} / \log \beta_n^H(L)$$

The results (Table 1) show that the ternary complexes are stable. The negative values of $\Delta \log K$ show that the formation of ternary complexes, MAL is less favoured compared to the corresponding binary complexes, ML. This may be due to the availability of lesser number of coordination sites for bonding of the secondary ligand, L on the primary complex, MA than on free metal ion⁵. The stability of the ternary complexes, MAL with respect to the ligand, L follows the order, NBAA > NMAA > NPAA. This order of stability is in accordance with the basicity of these ligands as also supported by their SUBS values. The stability of the binary complexes, ML also follows the same order. Although the butyl group in NBAA is bulkier than the methyl group in NMAA, the greater stability can be due to its inductive effect which increases the basicity of the ligand. Contrarily, the phenyl group in NPAA decreases the stability due to its steric hindrance and electron withdrawing (-I) inductive effect which decreases the basicity of the ligand.

The stability of the ternary complexes, MAL with respect to the ligand, A is : bipy > phen. The greater stability of bipy can be due to its better (metal \rightarrow bipy) $d\pi$ - $p\pi$ interactions⁵ and flexibility compared to phen. The stability of the complexes with respect to the metal ion follow the natural⁷ order : Cu^{II} > Ni^{II}.

Experimental

The ligands, NMAA, MBAA and NPAA were prepared by known procedures⁸ and their solutions were prepared

in ethanol. The bipy, phen, metal(II) salts and other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Doubly distilled water was used in the preparation of solutions and for all the titrations. The stock solutions of metal ions, HNO_3 and KOH were standardized by known procedures⁹. The pH-metric titration of 50 ml of acidified solution containing 1 : 1 : 1 (M : A : L) molar solution for ternary systems and 1 : 5 (M : L) molar solution for binary systems were carried out against standard solution of KOH in ethanol-water (50% v/v) medium at 30 °C and 0.1 M (KNO_3) ionic strength.

The proton-ligand (pK) and metal-ligand (ML) binary formation constants were determined by Irving-Rossotti method¹⁰. The formation constants of the ternary complexes were determined by known methods¹¹. The pH-metric readings in aqueous-ethanol were corrected by the method of Uitert and Haas¹².

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Note

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